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Testing insects in VR

Here, I assessed critical parameters of long-range search including reactive distance, motion parallax, anemotaxis, and plume following using a multimodal virtual reality (MultiMoVR) arena. Current technological limitations restrict the ability to produce arbitrary colour spectra, analogue odour and wind, and simultaneous comprehensive biomechanical feedback present in the real world. To account for these confounding variables, I presented dynamic and controlled stimulus feedback to tethered animals using VR stimuli and compared against observed real-world search behaviours to

assess the efficacy of my technique. This required a model system whose ecology and multimodal preferences were well-studied and stereotyped for specific objects. I thus chose the apple fly *Rhagoletis pomonella* as my model system. *R. pomonella* are specialist insects with adults of both sexes using specific visual and odour cues of ripe fruit in the tree canopy to locate sites for mating and oviposition^{27,132}. These multimodal cues are well-documented^{27,132}, as is an ethogrammatic description of fly orientation behaviour in the field^{6,27}. To this end, I provided photorealistic scenes and perspective-accurate stimuli of 3D tree models along with grass and sky textures in a 1,025 × 1,025-m landscape, including directional airflow and odour. This landscape was presented in a periodic boundary condition such that as the animal approaches the end of the virtual landscape, it is seamlessly placed at the opposite side, so the animal can essentially translate infinitely in any direction. Using this arena, I show that multiple Dipteran species, including a North American pest (*R. pomonella*), tropical vector (*Aedes aegypti*), Asian species (*Pselliophora laeta*), and cosmopolitan pollinator (*Eristalis tenax*), can navigate toward virtual 3D objects in a complex environment using this system. I then measure the reactive distance^{24,25,26} of *R. pomonella* to objects during long-range search. I also show that *R. pomonella* utilizes motion parallax to discriminate virtual objects of varying sizes and distances in a complex 3D environment, respond to directional airflow based on velocity, and orient to directional odour flux in VR. I finally discuss how this evidence opens avenues of exploration for a variety of biological and technological applications.

4.1 LOCALIZATION OF VIRTUAL ECOLOGICALLY RELEVANT OBJECTS IN A COMPLEX ENVIRONMENT

To determine if insects approached virtual visual objects, the VR was initialized with four worlds: virtual object on the left, object on the right, no object, and objects on both sides. The gain was set based on a species' optimal range as calculated above, with 1 m/s translational velocity and reset

time. The reset time was scaled to provide enough time for the insect to reach a faraway object, that is, twice the line-of-sight time taken to the virtual object. The insect was placed in the next virtual world and reinitialized after each reset event (See section 3.7 on page 55). Every world was repeated 10 times for each insect or until it stopped flying. The distance assay was repeated with the insect placed at different initial positions to measure response in VR.

Using the aforementioned calculated gain (see section 3.8), I first characterized the behaviour of apple flies in the presence of virtual tree-like objects (Figure 4.2 on page 66). In a world with only grass and sky, the flies did not choose to translate in any particular virtual direction, indicating that they did not localize or navigate to any aspect of the scenery such as a cloud or a patch of grass (Figure 4.2 on page 66); n

= 11 flies, n = 103 trials, trial duration 15 s, Rayleigh test mean angle -17.83° , $R = 0.062$, $z = 1.809$, $P = 0.634$).

This also indicates that static elements in the insect's field of view such as bezels, capillaries, and the camera did not evoke any gaze fixation as evidenced by the lack of any specific direction in this landscape and as observed in previous VRs^{15,28,29,30,31}. However, when provided a tree, flies fixated on and approached the tree, and exhibited stereotypical object avoidance/landing responses with

Figure 4.1: Virtual trajectories of apple fly to worlds with a tree on left and tree on both sides, at 3 m virtual distance (N = 11 flies, n = 103 trials). **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001. Polar plots representing corresponding mean angles for each trajectory.

Figure 4.2: (A and B) Virtual trajectories of *R. pomonella* (apple fly) to worlds with no tree (A) and a tree on the right (B), at a 3-m virtual distance (n = 11 flies, n = 103 trials). (C) Virtual trajectories of *P. laeta* (crane fly) to a tree on the right, at a 4-m virtual distance (n = 6 flies, n = 15 trials). (D) Virtual trajectories of *A. aegypti* (yellow fever mosquito) to a tree on the right, at a 3-m virtual distance (n = 6 flies, n = 13 trials). (E) Virtual trajectories of *E. tenax* (hoverfly) to a 1-m-high flower on the right, at a 1-m virtual distance (n = 2 flies, n = 6 trials). **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001. All polar plots provide corresponding mean angles for each trajectory, with the black line indicating the total mean.

rapid saccades (rapid body turns within the tree canopy) and foreleg extension when within <10 cm of elements in the canopy^{133,134} (Figure 4.1 on page 65; n = 11 flies, n = 103 trials, trial duration 15 s, Rayleigh test mean angle 42.54°, R = 0.306, z = 1.809, P = 4.69e-07). This indicates that flying insects can distinguish, navigate, and respond to virtual 3D objects from the surrounding visual scenery. In a world with two identical trees, flies oriented and approached both trees equally, as described previously for field behaviour²⁷ (Figure 4.1 on page 65; n = 11 flies, n = 103 trials, trial duration 15 s, Rayleigh test mean angle 4.692°, R = 0.22, z = 1.809, P = 0.634).

Along with a pest (apple fly), I also measured localization of virtual tree-like objects in a crane fly (*P. laeta*; Figure 4.2 on page 66 and Figure 4.3 on page 67; n = 6 flies, n = 15 trials, trial duration 15 s, Rayleigh test mean angle -25.56°, R = 0.445, z = 1.666, P = 1.00e-05; Movie S3). I also tested a disease vector (male mosquito, *A. aegypti*; Figure 4.2 on page 66 and Figure 4.4 on page 68; n = 6

Figure 4.3: Virtual trajectories of crane fly to worlds with no tree, tree on left and tree on both sides, at 3 m virtual distance (N = 6 flies, n = 15 trials). **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001. Polar plots representing corresponding mean angles for each trajectory.

flies, n = 13 trials, trial duration 15 s, Rayleigh test mean angle -24.19° , $R = 0.390$, $z = 2.400$, $P = 0.005$; Movie S3). I also used virtual flowers for a pollinator (hoverfly, *E. tenax*; Figure 4.2 on page 66 and Figure 4.5 on page 68; n = 2 flies, n = 6 trials, trial duration 30 s, Rayleigh test mean angle -16.35° , $R = 0.488$, $z = 1.429$, $P = 0.007$; Movie S3).

I show that all four species can distinguish, navigate, and respond to virtual 3D objects from the surrounding background. In addition, hoverflies are eponymous in their ability to hover over objects just before landing. To observe search behaviour in the final moments before landing, I closed the loop for both heading and flight speed for hoverflies. I used the wing-beat amplitude sum scaled appropriately in closed loop (SI Appendix, Methods, hoverfly experiments) to control the virtual flight speed and preliminary results show the possibility of virtual hovering in my arena (last 20 s of Movie S3). my experiments show that multiple insect species can search and navigate to 3D virtual

Figure 4.4: Virtual trajectories of mosquito to worlds with no tree, tree on left and tree on both sides, at 3 m virtual distance (N = 6flies, n = 13trials). **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001. Polar plots representing corresponding mean angles for each trajectory.

Figure 4.5: Virtual trajectories of hoverfly to worlds with no flower, flower on left and flower on both sides, at 1m virtual distance (N = 2flies, n = 6trials). Polar plots representing corresponding mean angles for each trajectory. ** P < 0.01.

objects in a complex landscape with ground and sky over large spatial scales.

4.2 DETERMINATION OF REACTIVE DISTANCE USING PERSPECTIVE CUES

In preliminary analyses, subtle differences in lighting, angle of the virtual sun, or perspective could cause changes in object preference, indicating that the 3D nature of the object might be important. For example, when two identical but asymmetrical 3D objects are placed equidistant from the observer in space, the objects will appear different from the observer's viewpoint (Figure 4.7 on page 70). This phenomenon is fundamentally unique to 3D geometry and is impossible to

Figure 4.6: Hexbinned plots of apple fly trajectories against trees placed at 3, 6, 12, and 24 m from the initial position ($n = 20$ flies, $n = 129$ trials). $**P < 0.01$, $***P < 0.001$. Violin plots indicate angles with respect to (w.r.t.) the tree at different distance bins.

recreate with identical 2D objects or even 3D objects that are symmetrical such as cylinders and spheres. To account for this and prevent side bias, all objects were mirror-flipped with respect to the vertical to present both trees from the same initial perspective to the insect. This suggests for a closer look at subtle perspective cues that might be utilized by flies.

To assess the effect of perspective regarding 3D objects, I assessed the response of apple flies

Figure 4.7: Two identical 3D models placed side-by-side and viewed equidistantly from the centre. Due to parallax, perspective, point of view and structural complexity, the two trees look different from each other.

Figure 4.8: Virtual trajectories of apple flies towards trees placed at 3, 6, 12, and 24 m from the initial position ($n = 20$ flies, $n = 129$ trials).

to identical virtual trees at different distances. Distant trees were less likely to be fixated on or approached (Figure 4.8 on page 70 and Figure 4.6 on page 69; $n = 20$ flies, $n = 129$ trials, trial duration 10, 15, 30, and 60 s; Rayleigh test at 3, 6, 12, and 24 m and no tree conditions, respectively; mean angle -11.47° , -7.83° , -0.64° , 10.47° , -17.83° ; $R = 0.48, 0.27, 0.34, 0.19, 0.06$; $z = 2.785, 3.001, 2.694, 2.294, 1.809$; $P = 9.54e-11, 9.79e-07, 1.08e-07, 0.05, 0.634$). Flies navigated to 16m^2 tree models up to a maximum distance of 24 m, as predicted by field data (37). As such, I was able to quantify the reactive distance of apple flies to their host during a long-range search, which indicates the limits of their visually guided object localization.

4.3 DECOUPLING SIZE AND DISTANCE USING MOTION PARALLAX

To differentiate the effects of object size and distance, I also presented apple flies with two tree objects, one twice as big and twice as far as the other tree such that, at the starting location, the trees subtended the same angular size. The flies oriented and approached the smaller, closer tree more frequently than the larger, farther tree (Figure 4.9 on page 71 and Figure 4.10 on page 72;

Figure 4.9: Virtual trajectories of apple flies for large distant trees vs. small nearby trees that subtend identical visual angles at the initial position ($n = 9$ flies, $n = 96$ trials, binomial test). $**P < 0.01$, $***P < 0.001$. Red circles indicate the starting position.

$n = 9$ flies, $n = 96$ trials, trial duration 30 s; binomial test for large vs. small and small vs. large trees,

respectively; $z = 3.022, 2.586$; $P = 0.001, 0.004$).

However, when both trees were equally far, they showed no preference for either tree (Figure 4.9 on page 71 and Figure 4.10 on page 72; $n = 9$ flies, $n = 96$ trials, trial duration 30 s; binomial test for small vs. small and large vs. large, respectively; $z = 0.482, 0$; $P = 0.315, 0.5$).

This shows that apple flies can make use of both object size and distance information obtained from localized motion parallax cues from rate of increase of angular size or relative side scrolling cues (discussed further in 5.2) to discriminate and navigate to objects for search behaviour. This indicates that complex visual processing is utilized for choosing targets in a complex world.

Figure 4.10: Hexbinned plots of apple fly trajectories against large distant trees vs. small nearby trees that subtend identical visual angles at the initial position ($n = 9$ flies, $n = 96$ trials, binomial test). $**P < 0.01$, $***P < 0.001$. Red circles indicate the starting position.

4.4 ORIENTATION TO DIRECTIONAL AIRFLOW IN THE ABSENCE OF OPTIC FLOW

To assess if insects can make use of cues from directional airflow in the absence of optic flow, I characterized trajectories of apple flies placed in different wind tunnel-like airflow fields (here called “windfields”) and velocities in a visually featureless environment (zero optic flow; Figure 4.14 on page 74).

To measure if insects could make use of directional airflow

Figure 4.11: Based on the windfield and the fly’s virtual position and heading, the appropriate set of capillaries continuously provides directional airflow cues.

cues provided using the windscape, VR was initialized with four worlds: open-loop windfield, easterly, westerly, and northerly.

In the open windfield case, regardless of the insect's position or heading, the insect always received directional airflow from a single capillary at the front of the insect. In the other three cases, based on the insect's position and heading, the directional airflow was altered to provide that particular windscape at the current insect position and orientation. This entire assay was repeated at different airflow velocities. I use this term rather than "wind" to clarify that tethered insects are not advected and therefore do not experience the complete mechanosensory feedback they would experience in true wind. In closed loop, the airflow was presented to the animal from different capillaries depending on its orientation with respect to the global windfield (Figure 4.11 on page 72).

At zero airflow, flies did not orient in any particular direction (Figure 4.13 on page 74 and Figure 4.12 on page 73; $n = 22$ flies, $n = 158$ trials, trial duration 15 s, Rayleigh test mean angle -80.97° , $R = 0.19$, $z = 2.551$, $P = 0.24$). But, as windfield velocities increased, flies oriented more in the downwind direction as suggested by previous studies (31, 38)

Figure 4.12: Hexbinned virtual trajectories in zero optic flow and different airflow velocities, 0, 1, 2, 3, and 3 m/s + tree ($n = 22$ flies, $n = 158$ trials). Violin plots of angle with respect to wind in different directional airflow speeds. ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Figure 4.13: Virtual trajectories of apple fly in zero optic flow and different directional airflow velocities, 0 m/s, 1 m/s, 2 m/s, 3 m/s (N=22 flies, n=158 trials). **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001.

(Figure 4.13 on page 74

and Figure 4.12 on page

73; n = 22 flies, n = 158

trials, trial duration 15 s; Rayleigh test for 1, 2, and 3 m/s, respectively; mean angle 137.7° , 177.51° , -160.97° ; R = 0.28, 0.43, 0.63; z = 2.551, 3.775, 2.785; P = 2.04e-08, 1.09e-05, 9.44e-07).

To account for potential artefacts produced by mechanical deflections of the wing at high wind speed, I placed a tree upwind in this high-velocity windfield. In this scenario, flies flew upwind toward the tree, indicating that they could orient upwind at these windfield velocities given an appropriate visual context (i.e., tree-like object; Figure 4.13 on page 74 and Figure 4.12 on page 73; n = 22 flies, n = 158 trials, trial duration 15 s, Rayleigh test for 3 m/s + tree, mean angle -3.20° , R = 0.14, z = 2.004, P = 3.23e-03).

Figure 4.14: The visual scenery with zero optic flow.

I also presented global windfields as either open-loop, northerly, easterly, or westerly. In the open-loop scenario, the airflow was always delivered from the front capillaries regardless of fly orientation and the flies displayed no preferred heading (Figure 4.15 on page 75). But in a directional

windfield such as easterly, where the wind blows from east to west, the flies oriented westward and maintained their downwind heading (Figure 4.15 on page 75; $n = 5$ flies, $n = 58$ trials, trial duration 15 s; Rayleigh test for open-loop, easterly, northerly, and westerly windfields, respectively; mean angle 56.36° , 102.76° , -163.65° , -64.82° ; $R = 0.085$, 0.892 , 0.756 , 0.862 ; $z = 1.591$, 1.512 , 1.512 , 1.511 ; $P = 0.18$, $0.1e-03$, $7.5e-05$, $0.12e-03$).

This indicates that the flies actively oriented using directional airflow cues provided by my virtual windscape even in the absence of optic flow.

4.5 AIRFLOW AND ODOUR ACT SYNERGISTICALLY FOR VIRTUAL PLUME FOLLOWING

Finally, I tested apple flies in a wind tunnel-like odour flux and windscape. Several studies have shown that in real-world turbulent conditions, odours exist in the form of plumes composed of intermittent packets of odour interspersed with clean air. Thus, odour is detected by flying insects as flux rather than a smooth concentration gradient, and insect antennae are flux detectors that respond to instantaneous changes in concentration rather than the absolute concentration at any moment^{135,136}. To accommodate these requirements in my arena, I presented a known attractive fruit blend odour¹³⁷ for *R. pomonella* as

Figure 4.15: Virtual trajectories against zero optic flow and different windfields: open loop, easterly, northerly, and westerly winds at 3 m/s (Rayleigh test, $n = 5$ flies, $n = 58$ trials). Violin plots indicate angle with respect to north in different windscape directions. Red dots indicate the starting location. ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

intermittent pulses placed in virtual space over a 2-m-wide strip that increased in frequency as the flies approached the virtual odour source, starting from 1 to 10 Hz over 20 m (Figure 4.16 on page 76). This simulated the punctate nature of odour information in an odour plume. I note that concentration could also be adjusted separately at a speed of up to 5 Hz through software control of the digital mass flow controllers as shown previously for this stimulus system⁹⁹. However, given that insects primarily respond to flux, for the purposes of these experiments I varied only pulse frequency and not concentration. To provide final target cues, I placed a tree far away, such that the visual cues alone would not elicit upwind flight.

To assess response to odour, the VR was initialized with an open windfield (see above) and no odour, open windfield and odour, closed windfield and no odour, or closed windfield and odour. In the odour worlds, the odour was given as a 2-m-wide rectangular strip with a gradient of increasing packet frequency based on the insect's position, starting at 1-Hz frequency and increasing to 10 Hz over 25 m with 50-ms pulse length.

I then presented flies with four conditions.

The slip condition provided only visual slip based on heading and airflow velocity with no change in airflow direction, meaning that airflow cues were in an open loop as described in the previous section. The slip and odour condition provided visual slip and increasing odour frequency only from the frontal capillaries, with the fly starting in the centre of the odour strip but at a 45° angle. The slip and windfield condition provided visual slip and a global windfield at 0.2 m/s as described above. Finally, the slip, windfield, and odour con-

Figure 4.16: Based on the fly's virtual position and odour-field, an odour pulse is released at the specified frequency.

dition provided all three parameters in a closed loop. Despite an initial cross-wind heading, flies remained significantly longer in the virtual odour plume region only when directional airflow + odour were combined (Figure 4.17 on page 77; $n = 8$ flies, $n = 33$ trials, Mann–Whitney U test with respect to the slip + windfield + odour condition, $U = 619$, $P = 0.026$).

Decoupling airflow

and odour stimuli showed that either stimulus alone did not result in significant time spent within the virtual odour plume over control (slip) conditions, as predicted by current anemotactic odour plume-tracking models (Figure 4.17 on page 77; $n = 8$ flies, $n = 33$ trials; Mann–Whitney U test with respect to slip for slip + odour and slip + windfield, respectively; $U = 769$, 735 ; $P = 0.292$, 0.254).

While both parameters are always coupled in nature, presenting airflow fields and odour flux in isolation allows us to quantify their relative contribution to upwind optomotor anemotaxis. My results suggest that both wind direction and odourflux must

Figure 4.17: Hexbinned plots of trajectories for visual slip, slip + odour, slip + windfield, and slip + windfield + odour ($n = 8$ flies, $n = 33$ trials). Pink gradient represents odourfield. Swarm plots indicate time inside plume regions. Red dots indicate the starting location. * $P < 0.05$, Mann–Whitney U test.

be present simultaneously for flying insects to orient within odour plumes.

4.6 THE PROBLEM OF LOW GAIN VR

To assess behaviour in these complex virtual environments, it was important to calibrate system gain to ensure that test insects were able to change direction to orient to multiple objects and stimuli. Interestingly, the arbitrary gain values used in previous studies have been much lower than the values I have calculated here (36 to 75 vs. 1 to 5 deg-deg⁻¹s⁻¹)^{16,53}). Low gain severely limits the range of angular velocities and manoeuvres insects can reliably perform. For example, the maximum angular velocity with such low gains is roughly 50 to 250 deg/s, while flies turning in free flight have been measured at 1,500 deg/s (12), which was attained in this study with the calculated gains. Thus, for analyses assessing navigation to objects with a calibrated ground and sky as shown here, it is suggested that gain be calculated for each species of interest. I note that my method to calculate gain was not effective in insects with wingbeat frequencies lower than 50 Hz, such as moths (*D. nerii*) and female crane flies (*P. laeta*). This is primarily due to the camera-tracking paradigm, which needs at least one full wingbeat cycle to measure wingbeat amplitude difference and lower wingbeat frequencies cause considerable latency to the system. Also, lower-wingbeat-frequency insects are likely to modulate flight parameters in multiple ways besides wingbeat amplitude difference, from changing angle of attack, abdomen position²⁹, to midstroke manipulation. Using a static torque sensor and/or tracking abdomen position in a closed loop would alleviate some of these challenges²⁹.

It is apparent from the Figure 3.13 on page 58 and Figure 3.14 on page 59 that there is no perfect gain and it is a fuzzy plastic region in which insects operate to cope with the dynamic environment they live in. But using the ability to perform a typical saccade as a yardstick for “normal flight performance”, a “normal” gain would enable the insect to attain typical saccade velocities of 2000 deg/sec. High and low gains would correspondingly suggest higher or lower max angular velocities. Based

on this premise, let us look at the choice of gains used in prior literature. In the seminal 1973 paper titled, “Pattern Induced Flight Orientation of *Musca Domestica*”, Reichardt and colleagues performed phenomenally rigorous set of experiments and devoted great efforts in the choice of gain. “A constant torque signal of 1 (dyne.cm) results in an asymptotic angular speed of 152.7 (degrees/sec) when coupling constant is $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (sec).” Their highest choice of gain (called coupling constant Θ/k) was $52 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (sec). This would result in a peak angular speed of 1976 deg/s. This peak value enables the fly to turn as fast as typical saccades. However, in recent studies^{16,94,109}, the gain values ranged around 5 (deg/deg/s). Depending on the max value of wingbeat amplitude difference (20-50 deg), this permits a peak velocity of only 100-250 deg/s which maxes out at $\frac{1}{10}$ of a typical saccade. A recent study¹³⁸ explicitly compares gains and does a great job. Their choice of “high” gain of 25 (deg/deg/s) max out at 500-1250 deg/s and is definitely a higher gain than most other literature in the field. However, the authors due to genuine technological constraints artificially capped the max angular velocity to 573 deg/s, which is only $\frac{1}{4}$ of a typical saccade. In our VR, we used gains as high as 96 (deg/deg/s) enabling peak velocities of 5000 deg/s. The loss of stability and total breakdown of optomotor response in a truly high gain scenario corresponds well with control theory literature. The choice of gain in the field has often been low and the reader can appreciate how severely low gains can make any control system simply too sluggish to be meaningfully functional. This also could explain why “saccades” last 10x longer in VR than free flight. In summary, I would advocate the VR community to perform gain calibration sweeps and use gain values that are “optimal” for their model system.

4.7 AUGMENTING FIELD ECOLOGY USING VR

Using my calculated “optimal” gain, I show that *R. pomonella* flies can approach tree-like objects ($4 \times 4 \times 4$ m) from up to roughly 24 m away and prefer to approach closer objects even if they are

smaller. While 2D patterns can be used to measure visual acuity, these stimuli cannot measure how far the animal will localize and navigate to an object of interest. This value is a critical parameter for ecological models such as reactive space, optimal foraging, dispersal rates, and several other contexts^{7,8,9,10,11,13,32,35,33,116}, but is difficult to measure empirically without being able to track the insect in space and time. For example, determining the localization limits of insects can be used to optimize pest management strategies such as trap placement, increase pollination efficiency with better crop planning, and enhance repellent strategies for vectors.

Navigational models using landmarks and cognitive maps³⁷ presume the use of motion parallax to distinguish aspects of the surrounding landscape. By presenting multiple objects of different sizes and distances, I show that local motion parallax is actually used by flying insects to discriminate and localize 3D virtual objects amidst a complex background. To date, most of these parameters have been assessed in walking insects, where stimulus space is calibrated and insect trajectory can be monitored^{19,20}. While similar models are postulated for flying insects such as honey bees, the precise use of these features previously remained elusive due to the inability to dynamically manipulate the landscape in space and time^{21,22}. I note that motion parallax causes differences in expansion rates and also causes differential optic flow based on distance. Which of these mechanisms are being utilized in the observed response requires further study.

Additionally, I found that *R. pomonella* flies could utilize windfield cues for orientation in the absence of optic flow, which has important implications for understanding navigation and migration of flying insects, particularly at high altitudes^{42,41} (Fig. 3 B and C). Studies with migrating insects and marine species suggest that organisms advected by flow can measure the flow velocity of the medium indirectly by measuring the curl¹³⁹ and jerks⁴¹ of the eddies due to turbulence. Although the mechanosensory input that a tethered insect receives will differ from a free-flying individual, my study demonstrates the intrinsic ability of *R. pomonella* to modulate behaviour in response to air-flow speed and direction. While these results do not negate the use of optomotor anemotaxis, they

provide a putative mechanism as to how flying insects could navigate in the absence of optic flow, such as high-altitude and nighttime migrations. For example, flight mills, vertically facing radar, and harmonic radar tracking are commonly used techniques to understand migration and dispersal but cannot simultaneously measure the precise location of the insect and the sensory stimuli it is receiving at that moment^{42,41,140,141}. In addition, the inability to dynamically manipulate these stimuli limits the ability to assess the effects of wind direction, wind speed, visual slip, landmarks, and horizon on individual behaviour. These aspects are fundamental parameters in determining the distance and direction of migration patterns and have important implications for population-level movement and dispersal of pests, predators, and disease vectors and their management^{42,140}.

4.8 THE POWER OF MULTIMODAL VR

Finally, I show that *R. pomonella* flies can respond to intermittently pulsed odour stimuli as predicted by current plume-following models, and show how my system can decouple each component of chemically mediated optomotor anemotaxis^{13,14,141,142}. Wind tunnels are commonly used in studying plume-following behaviour but cannot easily be utilized to assess and decouple the effects of dynamic wind and odour cues as examined here^{143,142,144,13,6,7,8}. Deconstructing the strategies and algorithms underlying plume-following behaviour is a long-standing problem in biology and engineering applications, and has been hampered by an inability to fully quantify stimulus and response⁶⁸. Decoupling vision, wind, and odour in plume following provides insights into the relative importance of each of these modalities in a behaviour used in almost every aspect of insect life.